

ANALYSIS OF REVOLUT BANK AND ITS INNOVATIVE SERVICES

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Abstract: This article provides detailed information about Revolut Bank, one of the international digital banks, and analyzes its main financial indicators in detail.

Keywords: Revolut Ltd., innovative services.

Introduction. An effective way to quickly and efficiently develop the banking system is, first of all, to analyze the experience of developed countries and take the necessary aspects from them and apply them to our own banking system. The reason is that, considering that they have already moved forward, there is no point in creating the techniques and technologies that were developed in them. Therefore, our task is to study the foreign experience, get the aspects that we need, and then continue to create new innovations. It is for this reason that we analyze below the international digital bank of a developed country with many years of experience.

Research methodology. Statistical tables in this study, logical and comparative analysis, grouping methods, as well as research works and statistical data of the bank's official website were widely used.

Analysis and results. Revolut Ltd. Group (Great Britain). Revolut Ltd. – Revolut was founded in the UK in 2015 and offers faster and cheaper money transfers and currency than legacy banks. Seven years later, more than 25 million retail customers in more than 35 countries worldwide (as of November 2022) use

Revolut's ever-growing range of powerful and easy-to-use products is using to control in the set.

Revolut Ltd (the "Company") and its subsidiaries (together the Group - the "Group") provide electronic money and payment services including prepaid card, currency exchange, P2P payments, cryptocurrency and commodity exposures, share trading, offers consumer loans and cards for retail users. It also offers a similar offering to business customers, including multi-currency exchange, prepaid corporate cards and international and local bank transfers to freelancers and SMEs.

Revolut is creating the world's first global financial super app. Revolut gives people and businesses more control over their finances and offers data-driven insights and personalization that empower our customers to make smarter decisions about how to spend, save or grow their money.

Revolut Group Ltd. services. Revolut is a virtual, app-based financial service. Revolut offers retail customers electronic money or bank accounts that they use for everyday spending and financial management. With four tiers starting with the free standard plan, customers can choose a plan that fits their financial lifestyle. Revolut offers a wide range of financial products, including - but not limited to - instant P2P payments, low-cost currency and multi-currency cards, micro-accounts, investment services for stocks, commodities and crypto-assets, apps, budgeting and analytics, donations, travel insurance, purchase protection and cover for missed events and tickets.

Revolut also provides business users with everything they need to manage their organization's day-to-day finances - with the speed and convenience of Revolut's retail product. As the retail and business ecosystems grow, the touchpoints between the two, such as Revolut's business-to-employer relationship (with early pay and on-demand payment) and business-to-customer relationships that offer rewards and discounts to Revolut customers and continues to add value to their relationship.

General retail customers. Customer growth has been strong throughout 2021. The number of Revolut customers exceeded 11 million at the end of 2020, and the number of global customers increased to 16 million by the end of 2021. Throughout 2021, there has been a significant increase in the number of users who engage more deeply with Revolut through its paid plans - Plus, Premium and Metals. During 2021, the number of users on paid tariff plans increased by 75%, indicating that customers are eager to use more features and benefits, and the number of weekly active users increased by 50%. This growth, combined with a 10% increase in average spend per user, reflects deeper integration into customers' daily spending and financial lives. In terms of customer experience, Revolut continued to improve its in-app navigation and out-of-app functionality and launched a browser extension that helps users find discounts when shopping online and quickly check Revolut card purchases.

Customer protection. Revolut has dedicated more resources to fraud detection and prevention, as well as educating its customers on how to protect themselves against all types of fraudsters, in line with regulatory requirements and industry-recognized best practice. In cases where its customers are at risk of being exploited by fraudsters, Revolut has implemented additional controls to alert Revolut of such activity and prevent such fraud and customer interactions by applying sophisticated machine learning models.

Product innovation. In 2021, Revolut continued to rapidly introduce customer-focused products and expand its services to meet the growing needs of its customers. In addition to the many feature and design improvements introduced throughout the year, the following important products were released:

Stays: Stays builds on Revolut's travel-based origins, allowing users to book hotels and accommodations in the Revolut app and earn up to 10% cash back on bookings. In February 2022, Stays was updated to enable "book now, pay on property" clauses and position Stays as a real alternative to other booking services in the travel-tech space.

Payment on demand. Pay on Demand is Revolut's new payroll access product that gives Revolut users instant access to a portion of their payroll as soon as they get paid. It's easy to use and gives employees more control and flexibility over their finances. Pay on Demand is a great example of the potential and opportunities Revolut has by offering a business product alongside a retail product. In this case, Revolut can add value to both the employer and the consumer, as well as at other touchpoints where businesses and customers interact.

Interest Savings Banks: In a hyper-inflationary economy, users are becoming more and more careful about where they keep their savings. As Revolut's mission is to help people achieve financial independence and make the most of their money, it will continue to improve savings bank interest rates by working with selected partner banks. After first launching interest cashiers in the US in 2020, in 2021 Revolut introduced interest offers to customers in the UK and Poland.

Expenses: In March, we launched Expenses, an expense management tool for Revolut Business users. By using Expenses, business owners can get a complete view of their business finances and expenses. They can receive real-time expense notifications, set spending limits, block and freeze company cards, and review expenses within the app.

Revolut Shopper: To build on our out-of-app offering, Revolut has launched the free Revolut Shopper Google Chrome extension. Once installed, Shopper automatically finds and applies discount codes at online store checkouts. When shopping with reward partners, customers can receive cash back into their Revolut account on top of any discount codes applied by the extension when shopping with its partners.

Financial circumstances

2021 revenue up 190% year-on-year to £636m (2020: £220m). The revenue was driven by continued customer growth across Revolut's retail and business ecosystems, with retail customer numbers up 46% year-on-year.

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Gross margin increased to nearly 70 percent in 2021 from 33 percent in 2020, driven by an increased share of revenue from high-margin products such as currency and wealth, as well as improved margins on payment operations due to cost optimization initiatives. Our business continued to track operating leverage due to cost discipline execution, with operating expenses increasing 37% year-to-date in 2020 and gross profit increasing 512% year over year. Chose to reinvest revenue into customer growth by expanding our marketing function by launching digital marketing and referral campaigns. Thanks to improved gross margins and operating leverage, Revolut has turned profitable for the first time in 2021, with a profit from operations of £59.1m in 2021 and a total of £19.7m in total revenue for the year.

1st table.

Summary report on the financial situation [www.revolut.com – Revolut bank's official website open data.],

(in thousands of pounds)

Balance	December 31, 2021	December 31, 2020	January 1, 2020
Assets			
Current assets			
Cash and cash equivalents	7,052,609	5,055,023	2,462,986
Financial assets in FVOCI	1,236,481	-	-
Investments in goods at FVTPL	66,356	50,366	-
Trade and other receivables	206,880	153,242	209,825
Inventory	7,396	11,282	13,042
Current tax assets	7,291	3,856	1,693
Loans and advances to customers	4,870	415	-
Derivative financial assets	9,294	121	-
Total current assets	8,591,177	5,274,305	2,687,546
Turnover assets			
Property, equipment and right-of-use assets	25,128	37,497	38,424
Intangible assets	721	411	93,927
Loans and advances to customers	12,946	961	-
Deferred tax assets	1,783	345	42
Total non-current assets	40,578	39,214	132,393
Total assets	8,631,755	5,313,519	2,819,939
Liabilities and capital			
Current liabilities			

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Trade and other payables	165,248	143,663	203,830
Loans at amortized cost	122	81,812	972
Accounts payable	7,361,196	4,637,230	2,367,200
Current tax liabilities	9,374	1,670	-
Lease liabilities	5,161	5,985	3,593
Derivative financial liabilities	2,454	1,970	-
Total current liabilities	7,543,555	4,872,330	2,575,595
Long-term liabilities			
Credits for amortized costs	-	-	119,546
Reserves for liabilities	1,812	1,788	1,775
Lease liabilities	9,085	18,943	23,104
Deferred tax liabilities	243	18	-
Total long-term liabilities	11,140	20,749	144,425
Total liabilities	7,554,695	4,893,079	2,720,020
Capital			
Authorized capital	-	-	-
Share premium	1,287,452	697,444	248,814
Accumulated deficit	(317,960)	(344,300)	(159,337)
Other reserves	107,568	67,296	10,442
Total capital	1,077,060	420,440	99,919
Total liabilities and equity	8,631,755	5,313,519	2,819,939

From the table above, we can see that Revolut bank's important balance indicators, i.e. total assets and total liabilities and capital amount to 2.8 billion, respectively, in 2 years. increased from 8.6 billion. Of this, almost 8.5 billion of assets were formed at the expense of current assets. From this we can see that the bank focused on short-term operations, so long-term operations are very small - 40 million pounds.

2nd table.

Income structure [www.revolut.com – Revolut bank official website open data.], (in thousands of pounds sterling)

	2021	2020
Revenue	636,205	219,931
Selling price	(196,015)	(148,063)
Total income	440,190	71,868
Administrative expenses	(367,478)	(274,701)

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Depreciation and amortization expenses	(9,079)	(9,629)
Value (loss) / credit	(1,034)	220
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Other operating (expense) / income	59,091	(205,461)
Interest expense	(21,026)	(17,373)
Interest income	1,726	2,129
Profit before tax / (loss)	39,791	(220,705)
Tax (expense) / credit	(13,451)	(2,917)
Net profit / (loss) for the year	26,340	(223,622)
Other total income		
Income from revaluation of intangible assets (cryptocurrencies)	-	38,659
Currency translation differences	(9,237)	(328)
Gain from fair value on financial assets held at fair value through comprehensive income	2,602	-
Other comprehensive (loss)/income, net of taxes	(6,635)	38,331
Total Total Income / (Loss) for the year	19,705	(185,291)

In table 2, if we pay attention to the income of Revolut banking in 2021 and 2020, it was almost 72 million pounds in 2020 and 440 million in 2021. However, the net income of the bank decreased slightly and amounted to 26 million due to the costs of its internal division.

Summary. Thus, when we analyze a digital bank with an international high rating, it is distinguished by its originality. It is different not only in the design of the bank's brand, platform or mobile applications, but also in the types of services and goals it provides to customers. In addition, he prefers to work on individual products rather than creating standard products that are common to all customers. Also, the international digital bank is very open and flexible to innovation, use of

innovative technologies. And finally, it works not only for profit, but for the purpose of improving people's lives even a little, and he is loyal to his values.

References:

1. www.revolut.com – official website of Revolut bank open data.
2. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Revolut>

